

A Marketing of Innovative E-Financial Services with Reference to SBI and ICICI Bank

Dr. Riazuddin Ahmed,
Assistant Professor,

Department of Business Management & Accounting,
Komar University of Science & Technology, Sulamaiya region, Kurdistan

Abstract:- Electronic Financial services is consists of the financial market such as Bank ,Non banking financial Institutions, etc. and theses e-Financial Institution transfer the financials services from saving to investments. These Services rendered by the Financials institutions are called as Financial Services. Median defines financial services activities. This e-financials sector has been growing in term of number and quality financial of services. After the liberalization of Indian Economy in 1990s, the number of financial services is increasing day by day. New trends and Innovative financial Services have been recognized. These include Commercial Banks, Insurance Companies, merchant banking, institutions, mutual funds, factors, leasing and hire purchase, credit rating, agencies, finance companies etc.

The e-financial services mean allocation and mobilization of savings and resources. This includes transformation of financial activities into saving into investments. Financial services means the services provided by the financial institutions, These financials institutes consist of a range of organisations which deals managing money, These institutions includes investments banks, brokerages services, insurances services, consumers financials institutes, and non banking financial services etc. Financial Intermediate means collecting the funds from various group of customer funds and make the funds available for those who need the money in terms of loans to those individual and corporate companies. This institution which helps financial services like banks, investment firms, merchant banks, leasing, and venture capital mutual funds companies etc. These financial services provide operation to the financial markets.

I. INTRODUCTIONS

Financial services is consists of the financial market such as Bank, Non banking financial Institutions, etc. and theses Financial Institution transfer the financials services from saving to investments. These Services rendered by the Financials institutions are called as Financial Services. Median defines financial services activities.

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Innovative Financial Services as defined by the General Agreement on Trade and Services (GATS) consist of insurance services, banking services and other Financial Services. Insurance services cover direct insurance (life and non –life) reinsurance, insurance service including consultancy actuarial, risk Management and claim and settlement of Insurance services, defined under GATS to include acceptance of deposits, lending, financial leasing, payment and money transmission services, guarantees and commitments, trading in money market instruments and foreign exchange, derivative products, interest rate instruments, transferable securities, other negotiable instruments participations in issue of securities, money broking, assets managements, portfolio, management etc,

A. Financials Services Features:

➤ Intangibility Financial Services :

Some of the tangible products like furniture, computer, Television, and soaps, shampoos etc are we can see, touch and feel in the tangible products where as in case of the financial services are intangible.

➤ *Direct Sales in Financial Services:*

Direct Sales of financial services provides services to Individuals, Corporate etc. These DS (Direct Sales) creates only the channel of distributions like DSA, Agencies like Insurance agents etc.

➤ *Different Need Financial Services:*

Financial Services are satisfying the different needs in financials areas. These Financial Services Institutions or Banks have to offer a innovative Products & Financial Services to the customers. The implication of financial services is to standardized in term of product, Price and Promotional etc.

➤ *Changing in Demand of Customers:*

As the customer need is changing and the demand of financial services are all ways changing. for a example the life insurance, and other financial services are all ways changing according to the level of economic activity.

II. TYPES OF FINANCIAL SERVICES

Financial service institutions provide a various types of financials of services to meet the different requirements of individual, corporate customers. These services includes.

A. *Equipment Financing and Leasing:*

Equipment Financing or leasing is an agreement with the firm to acquires and make use of a capital asset like machinery, Equipment, furniture etc, A leasing is the agreement between the two parties,. The person (or the company) which acquires the machinery has the right is known as lessee. He does not have ownership right. He has only the right to use the asset. The person (or the Company) who gives the right is known as less or.

B. *Hire Purchase Instalments:*

Hire purchase is a type of financial services where the purchased and sales of the goods are on the agreement on the credit basis. The payment system will on the instalment basis. The buyer will not he ownership rights unless he pays all the instalment or clear the instalment, After the payment of the all instalment, if the buyer fails to pay the any one of the instalments the seller can be repossess the good sold, each of the instalment are divided into equally monthly instalment which includes interest rates.

C. *Venture Capital:*

Venture capital means an capital refers to financial institution. The services renders by the financial institution is to provide a equity finance to the small businessmen and play a important role in providing an advising and consulting their management..

D. *Mutual Funds:*

Mutual funds mean the combination or financial intermediaries which mobilise the saving form the individual, corporate or government securities. The mutual funds manage the money of societies and generate income through dividends, interest and capital gains. The income are

manages buy the fund manager based on shareholders, on fund based financial services.

➤ *Indian Financials Services:*

The Financials Service means activities which are of financial in nature and also called financial Services. A Median defined financial services as “activities Benefits and satisfactions connected with the sale of money that offers to individual who uses the financial services. The financial sector forms a significant part of the financials services. This sector has been continuing to grow in term of number and quality of services. After the liberalization of Indian economy in 1990s financial services are increasing day by day, The trends new innovative financials services have emerged and the traditional services are broadened. Suppliers of financial services include commercial banks, insurance, merchant banking institutions, mutual funds, factors, leasing and hire purchase, credit rating agencies, finance companies etc.

➤ *Innovative Financial Services In Banking Sector:*

Innovations in the financial services means something new in the product or services or application or new method of doing or marketing the product or services in financial services. The financial Services as defined as Marketing and promoting new Financials Products, developing new market segment, new Business model, to facilitate financials activities

➤ *New Trends In Marketing Innovative Financial Services In Banking Sector.*

- *Internet Banking:*

The delivery of innovative financial services of Bank to a customer at his office or home by using Internet delivery channels may be called Internet banking. It the application of electronic technology electronic for transfer of funds, though an electronic terminal, computer or magnetic tape and to conduct various transactions like cash receipts, payments, transfer of funds etc. it is any where, any time banking 24hr in day and 7 days in a week(24*7). The delivery of Internet banking product/ services by electronic channels also knows as Internet Banking. It started with the introduction of computers and ATMS (in 1970s).The next step was telephone banking (in 1980s) and now Internet banking. The introduction of new instruments such as credit cards, ATMS, Retail Banking Electronic Funds Transfer (EFT) and Electronic Clearing Services (ECS) have all helped in developing an effective and seedy payment and settlement system, Internet banking is slowly becoming popular in India, All these constituted electronic banking.

- *Social Banking:*

The Commercial Banks of Indian has adopted a new trends of policy to meet the Socio economic of the country banking systems, These important factor aspects of social factor are open to banks in rural branches area, of the country, provides credit facilities to the rural customers and small scale industries, banks have to formulate area wise schemes and plans, banks help in critical situations is disaster management like, floods, earthquakes, rains, etc.

SBI has taken some initiatives adoption schemes under financials development of the villages.

- *Computerizations Banking :*

The Computerized Banking was first introduced in banking and 1989. Indian Banking systems has adopted and installed around 4476 automatic ledger posting machines at the branch. They have trained around 2000 programmers and system designers and around 12000 data entry operators. firstly they initial started with computers in banking systems and today we see banks has come with long journey to diverse product and delivery channels to meet the need, demands and fulfil expectation of the customers today banks has find out demand conveniences of anywhere and anytime facilitates the global banking systems.

- *Telephonic Banking System:*

The Telephonic Banking system is an important product in banking sector. Customers can do number of transaction from their home or office or any where. The customer have to call to the telephonic no or help line number of the banks. The service is open for 24/7 around clock and with the security details provided with the operator. They can avail services such as check balances stop payments of the cheques. Information of transfer of the funds, bank statements etc. through the telephonic or phone banking.

- *Client Advisors System:*

The Client advisor services are also called as a financial Service Provider of the banks or Personal banker of the banks; they bankers provide a services of any information's about the product and services of the banks and allow verifications that he speaks as an authorised person from the banks. He provides services and products to the customer based on the request of from the customers, delete the products services.

- *Automatic Telephonic System (ATS) :*

These type of services can avail by the customer through the mobile or normal phone, The toll free no is connected the Automated Telephonic System is facilities the customer to do entire non cash related banking or telephonic, Under this System the customer line is connect with voice recorder which the customer can use a transaction. By press the button on the phone a customer can get information from the banker through the recorded voice systems. Some of the banks offer this type of the services free the customers.

- *ATM:*

Automatic Teller Machines is most popular in India as well as the in the world, which enables the customers to withdrawn their money 24hours a day and 7 days in a week, It is advises that customers not only to with draw the money but also to deposit money through the ATMS, The new trends also recognised in the ATMs like Cheque Deposit, Balance Transfer& Funds, Mobile Recharge and Pay the Utility bills.

- *E-Mail Banking:*

Electronic Mail banking is another trends in Financials Services, Is possible to communicate with the banking Customer by electronic mail or e-mail. The most frequently used E-mail Banking services in account statement at an agreed periodicity to the Customer mail box. E-mail Banking services are not used for banking transactions as a funds transfer and other operational services.

- *SMS Banking:*

Short Message Services in Banking services are another trends in Marketing of Innovative financial Services. In SMS banking system using customer mobile, it is used by all national and international banks and other financial institutions to message, notification or alert message. As soon as customer withdraw the money or transaction or any type of Cheque clearance or balance transfer an alert message automatically send to customer and balance message will be send to the mobile phone.

- *Internet Banking or Online Banking:*

Customers are provided access to bank via Internet. Coupled with computerizations of the branch network of each bank, The Reserve Bank of India suggested to all banks to network their branch offices for intra – bank connectivity for addressing for the twin issues of intra- banking funds transfer and transmission of critical MIS information between branches and controlled offices. Intra –Bank connectivity will ensure the funds department is connected to the controlling office on the one hand and with large business centres on the other.

- *Mobile Banking:*

Mobile Banking is new trends in area of Innovative Financials Services; The customer can do transaction like transfer of funds, recharge of mobile, pay utility bills through mobile Banking. Customer of the Mobile Banking has to download an app from the Smart phone through he can access the Product details of the Banks.

- *Electronic Funds Transfers (EFT) :*

Electronic Funds Transfer is a new trends in marketing Financial Services whereby anyone who wants to make payment to another person/ Company /school fees etc can approach to his bank and make the cash payment or give instruction to transfer the funds directly from his bank account to another account. Full detail of receiver account number, account type, bank name, branch name and has to requesting.

- *Virtual Banking:*

The term virtual banking is the type's electronic delivery of services. Basically, it means that the customer is not interact with the staff of the bank across branches. Most of the customers are now using electronic delivery financials services with virtual banking. They use new financials services such as credit cards, telebanking, ATMs, retail Banking, Electronic Funds Transfer (EFT) and Electronic Clearing Services (ECS).

- **Merchant Banking:**

Merchant Banking is the new method of selling. According to Coax the merchant banking defined as “Merchant banking are financial institution are providing the financial services which includes Bills of exchange, corporate finance, portfolio management and other banking services”. Services provided by merchant banks are corporate counselling, project counselling, issue of Share and debenture, bankers to the issues, portfolio management services. Another type of merchant banking services includes mergers and takes over, venture capital, leasing, corporate counseling, bill discounting, amalgamation and takeover, relief to sick industries etc.

- **Credit Cards:**

Credit is new technology development in the electronic banking system. It is also called as plastic money which mean buy know and pay latter. It's a chip based card, the most important is that the banker issues card based on the income of the customer. The limit is sanctioned based on the income of the customer. The user of the card can used the limit which bank has sanctioned the said limit. the customer can use the credit card up the limit the banker has sanctioned the limit and withdraw the money from the any atm. The bankers will provide him interest free period from 30 to 45 days,.

III. 4 IMPORTANT BANK MARKETING

According to Deryk Weyer, defines the Marketing strategies of the bank as the process to identifying the profits of markets, present and future, assessing the bank in presents and future needs of the consumers, their needs development the business strategies of the banks setup the target markets and managing the various financial needs of the customers.

A. Customers Awareness:

Customers awareness should be considered as an important factor in the bank marketing to increase awareness in the banking system, the should always conduct the marketing awareness program's to increase the customer awareness to know the product of financial services

B. Information Technology:

The information technology plays a vital role in development and customer awareness in the economic development and the financial system and banking. As the financial needs of the customer are changing, the customers want new technology should be adopted.as the various of the customer are identified and developed by the bankers such as quick financial services, accessibility, financials consultant, surplus funds, assets security, etc.

C. Quality Services as an Important Factor

With the adopting of new technology and economical development, fast changing economical activities banking system has not exempted from this changing. Quality has considered as an important factor in the banking systems. Which is considered as an marketing tools and banks has to changing to new trends in this scenario. Successful banks

have changed their services to quality as key factor to marketing crucial needs of the customers.

D. Competition

As the new marketing changing the demand of the customers and taste and preference also changes. As the competition is increasing in the banking sector, most of the Indian banks are also changed their way of doing their business. as enter of foreign banks the competition also increase in the Indian market. Competition has adopted new trends in technology with mobilization of resources, foreign and commercial banking providing superior services, speed transactions, and positioning with the quality of services in the minds of the customers.

IV. NEED FOR THE STUDY

The Study is concerned with the evaluation of overall Marketing of Innovative E- Financial Services in Banking sector –A comparative study.

To measure the performance of e-financial Services in banking sector with reference to SBI and ICICI Bank.

A. Objectives of the Study

- To Measure the Performance of E-Financial Services in Banking Sector with Reference to SBI and ICICI Bank
- To Study the Comparative Analysis of E-Financial Services in Banking Sector with Reference to SBI & ICICI .

- **HYPOTHESES H0:**

There is no significant difference in the Performance of Marketing of Innovative e-Financial Services in Banking Sector.

- **HYPOTHESES H0:**

There is no difference between customers towards Product, Pricing, Place and Promotional strategies of banks towards innovative e- financial services .

V. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Ravinder Reji Kumar (2012) has conducted the research study on the factor influence the decisions offline customers adopted mobile banking services in Kerala south India. With the help of the technology acceptance model the check the customer's satisfaction and online usage adaptation of the Indian banking. The finding of the study confirmed with those technology customers on the quality services.

Mohi-ud-Din Sangmi; Nazir, T. (2010) ² has found that financial sound health for the bank guarantee is not only deposits but also significant equally as such as shareholder, bank employees and economy as well.as an efforts have been form from measurement of time, and financials positions of each and every bank and manages efficiently.

Mitra, R. and Shankar, R. (2008)³ The study has confirmed that the stable and efficiency in the banking sector is more important to increase the economic development of the country. The study also confirmed that the model and evaluate of 50 Indian banking system using DEA(Data envelopment analysis),handling multiple systems inputs and outputs, can be analyzed by source of quantified evaluated units. The finding of the study supposed to accept or reject the hypothesis in banking to compete with the global competitors.

Prabha, Divya et al. (2006)⁴ has study the perception analysis's and the services quality of the large or big corporate in Tamil Naidu district in Coimbatore. This is based on SERQUAL scale based questionnaire for the survey analysis. The study based on the customers are more satisfied with services quality and dimension of quality services, The banks need to focus on communications, Time management of services and modernization of the banking services.

Laxman, G (2005)⁵ The study focus on the analyzed the performance of the Andhra Bank ATMS and level of satisfaction of ATMs Customer of the Andhra Bank. The study confirmed that the number of the ATMs availing services of the Andhra Bank. The finding of the study, majority of the customers from the middle and higher income profile and above the Educational factors holders expressed the good and very respondents' performance as a average factors.

Mariappan (2005)⁷ has study the factors on the technology and global banking services and observed that the IT enabled services has bought the many changes in the banking services. The study also revealed that banking services has includes by the advance technology and its services. The studies also focus on the EFT (Electronic Funds Transfer), Post (Point of Sales Terminals), EDI (Electronic Data Interchanged, Mobile Banking, Internet Banking etc.

Bhat, Mushtaq A. (2005)⁸ The study revealed that the Quality in Banking and Variation across demographic factors. The study has been collected from five different banks, SBI, PNB, J&K Bank, City Bank and SCGB Banks .The study focus on the service quality of foreign banks vs Indian Banks .The study revealed that the service quality of foreign bank is much better than the Indian Banks across demographic factors like age, income, occupations, locations etc.

Pai (2006)⁹ the study of Trends in the Indian Banking Industries" revealed that the inter regional credits and deposit of the banks. it also focus on the performance of the banks as a deposit and trade credits. It also focus on the private commercials banks as a superior performance. The study revealed that the growth as a parameters have been comparative between them.

Bodla et al. (2006)¹⁰ The study revealed that the performance of the SBI and ICICI Bank through the Camel Model. The study found the ICICI Bank has performed well than the SBI Bank in terms of earning in service quality, Operating profit ratio, net profit to average assets etc.

Bhayani et al. (2007)¹¹ The study focus on the Role of the transaction Cos in the Financial Performance of Corporative Banks have attempted to investigate how the proportion of transformation cost is higher than of transaction cost in the banks under study. Transaction cost plays an important role in the profitability.

Rajkumar (2007)¹² .the study revealed that the earning performance of the private sector bank in the period of 2005-2006 has reveals that the interest income over expenditure increase to Rs 13,108,Cr,during 2004-06,The increasing percentage was 31.the same time operating expenditure over the operating profit fell to over rs817 cr during the year 2005-06,from 992 cr during the year 2004-05, the profitability of the ratios of all the private 28 banks has positive responds during the year. The ICICI Bank stands highest among the profit of the banks.

Sinha et al. (2009)¹³ The study of this paper revealed that the Bank Ownership and Deposit Mobilization, a non parameters approach 'compare the performance of 40 Indian commercial banks using the windows analyzing, considering a deposit mobilization as a key indicator. The study results obtained from analysis is the technical mean efficiency was due to a greater performance compared to the frontier indicator. The conducted from the samples banks, the private banks performance is much better than the public sector banks.

Shobana (2010)¹⁴ the study revealed the operational efficiency of the public sector banks as a non parametric model' Focuses on the operational efficiency of public sector banks in India, using a non parametric model measure the ratio of output as index factor to index of output factor used. The finding of the study reveal that the output of 27 public sector banks in India and 9 had achieved high level of operational efficiency with Oriental Bank of Commerce as a top bank.

Verma et al. (2011)¹⁵ this paper focus on the performance of the scheduled commercial banks in India. An application of DEA analyze revealed that the efficiency of 88 SCBs with the data ranging from the year 1998-99 to 2007-2008, the results indicates the public and foreign banks has to reduce the expenses and improves the output at a given input level because theses failed to reached a full efficiency results scores in six.

Bhat, Mushtaq A. (2005)¹⁶.The study revealed that the quality service and the quality perceptual of Indian banking system comparative analysis with the foreign banks. SERVQUAL instrument model developed by parauraman et al in the year 1988. It has five dimensions model as factor such as reliability, responsiveness, empathy, assurance and tangibility were used to collect the primary data. A finding

of the study revealed that the Indian bank has below the average perceptual level of the customers in all dimension of service quality and foreign banks exceed the high perceptual level in the quality services.

Krishna Chithanya, V. (2005)¹⁷ the study revealed the financials activities in India and frame work of marketing strategy to attained a quality services. The study focus on the quality of services with the perceptual of actual services and customers expectations, it also suggested the 2 way channel for distribution financial services qualities such as TV mobile phones Computers etc.

VI. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Performance of Marketing Innovative Financial Services of the Selected Banks Analysis The sample of this is surveyed and the data analysis is done using the Primary Data from the Structured Questionnaire and Secondary Data from the various reports from the RBI Report, SBI Annual Banks Reports and ICICI Bank Annual Reports of Various Performances Report are tabulated with mean, standard deviation and the variance also the population of the samples response is analyzed with chi square technique.

Table 1 Shows Performance Analysis of No of Users E-Debit Card SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

YEAR	SBI BANK	% Change	ICICI BANK	% Change
2017	5.0	5.0	12.3	12.3
2018	11.0	11.0	11.3	11.3
2019	17.0	17.0	16.3	16.3
2020	28.30	28.30	27.6	27.6
2021	39.50	39.50	32.6	32.6

(Source From SBI Annual Performance Report and ICICI Performance Report)

From the table 1(1) Show the performance analysis of the no Users of the Debit Cards of SBI and ICICI Bank from 2017-2021. In the year 2017 SBI Debit cards users are 5% as comparer to the Users of ICICI Bank 12.3% in the Year 2017 the SBI and the ICICI Bank users are almost the same 11% in 2014 SBI has increase about 17% as compare to the ICICI Bank 16.3 %. In 2019 the SBI Bank has increase 28.30% where as compare ICICI Bank is at 27.6 % in 2020 the SBI Bank has 39.50 % increase where as compare to ICICI Bank at 32.6 % in 2021.

Table no : 1.1 Test of Hypothesis Testing:

H0: There is no significant difference in the Performance of E- Debit Card of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

Type of Account	Name of the Test	Degree of Freedom	Level of Significance	Value Calculated	Critical Value	Decision
Debit Cards	t-test	n1+n2-2	5%	0.492	2.31	Accepted.

Through T- Test, it is examined that there is no significant difference in the total Debit Cards uses of SBI and ICICI Bank. It can be discernible from the table the calculated value of t test is lesser than the critical value. Hence the hypotheses are accepted. It does mean that there is a significant difference in the users of debit cards of SBI and ICICI Bank.

Table 2 Shows Performance Analysis of No of E- Debit Card Transactions (Spending) SBI Bank and ICICI Bank.

YEAR	SBI BANK	% Change	ICICI BANK	% Change
2017	11073	9.12	116	13.11
2018	15443	12.72	124	14.01
2019	22407	18.45	166.99	18.87
2020	30785	25.36	215.35	24.34
2021	41681	34.33	262.38	29.65
Total	121389	100	884.72	100

From the Table: 2 The no of Debit Card Performance of the Total no of Transactions (Spending) of SBI and ICICI Bank Customers. In the year 2017 the SBI Bank is recorded as 11073 cores which is 9.12% as compare to the ICICI Bank total spending on debit card is 116 cores which is 13.11 %, In 2019 SBI Bank total debit card transaction is 22407 Cores is which is 18.45% where as the ICICI Bank is 166.99 Cores of Transactions which comes to 18.87 % which slightly more than the SBI Bank. In the year 2020 the SBI Bank recorded the Total no of Transaction 30785 which is 25.36% where as the ICICI Bank has recorded 215.35 cores of transaction on debit card which comes in percentage 24.34. which is less than the SBI Bank. In the year 2021 the Total SBI Bank no of transaction are recorded on SBI Debit Card transaction is 41.681 Cores that in percentage 34.33% Where as compare to ICICI Bank is 262.38 Cores of Transaction is recorded that is almost 29.65%

Table 2.1 Test of Hypothesis testing:

H0: There is no significant difference in the Performance of Total E- Debit Card Transaction of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

Type of Account	Name of the Test	Degree of Freedom	Level of Significance	Value Calculated	Critical Value	Decision
Debit Cards	t-test	n1+n2-2	5%	1.1526	2.31	accepted

From above Table the Through T- Test, it is examined that there is no significant difference in the Total Debit Cards Transaction of SBI and ICICI Bank. It can be discernible from the table the calculated value of t test is lesser than the critical value. Hence the hypotheses are accepted. It mean that there is a significant difference in users of Total Debit Cards Transactions of SBI and ICICI Bank.

Table 3 Shows Performance Analysis of No of E-Credit Card (Users) SBI BANK and ICICI BANK

YEAR	SBI BANK	% Change	ICICI BANK	% Change
2017	0.91	7.9%	2.5	16.12%
2018	1.28	11.21%	2.8	18.06%
2019	2.23	19.54%	3.2	20.64%
2020	2.31	20.24%	3.3	21.29%
2021	4.68	41.01%	3.7	23.87%
Total	11.41		15.5	

From the Table 3.0, the performance analysis of Credit Cards users of SBI Bank has decline in most of the years in 2017 is 0.91 lakhs which is in percent of 7.9 % where as the

ICICI Bank has recorded as 2.5 millions customers which comes is 16.12% of the customers which is more than SBI Bank. In the year 2017 SBI Bank increased the users of the credit card 1.28 which in 11.21% where as ICICI Bank has recorded 2.8 which in 18.06%. In the year 2019 the SBI Users was 2.23 which in percentage of 19.54 % where as ICICI Bank is recorded 3.2 millions users which is in 20.64%, which is more than of SBI Bank. In the year 2020 SBI Bank has recorded users of 2.31 millions which in 20.24% where as ICICI Bank has 3.3 which is in 21.29 % which is more than of SBI Bank. In the year 2021 SBI Bank is increased the 4.68 million users of credit cards customers which in 41.01% where as ICICI Bank has 3.7 million users which in 23.87% which is less than the SBI Bank in 2016.

Table 3.1 Test of Hypothesis Testing:

H0: There is no significant difference in the Performance of E- Credit Cards Users of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

Type of Account	Name of the Test	Degree of Freedom	Level of Significance	Value Calculated	Critical Value	Decision
Credit Cards	t-test	n1+n2-2	5%	13.4664	2.31	Rejected

Through T- Test, it is examined that there is no significant difference in the Credit Cards users of SBI and ICICI Bank. It can be discernible from the table the calculated value of t test is greater than the critical value. Hence the hypotheses are rejected. It does mean that there is a significant difference in the users of Credit Cards of SBI and ICICI Bank.

From the Table 4.0: the Performance of SBI Net Banking Users .In 2017 the no of Net Banking Users recording in SBI Bank is 30 million which in 8.74% where as compare to ICICI Bank it is 20 Million of Net Banking in 14.49% which is lesser than the SBI Bank. In 2018 the Total no of Users of SBI BANK is 38 which in 11.07% where as ICICI Bank has 25 million in 18.05% which lesser than of SBI Bank .In the year 2014, SBI Bank has recorded of 64 million of Net banking users in 18.65% where as ICICI Bank has 28 million users which in percentage is 20.21%, In the year 2015 SBI Bank has recorded 90 millions users which is in 26.23% where as ICICI Bank has 31.45 millions in 22.70%, In the year 2016 the SBI Bank net banking users are increase 121 million which in 35.27%.Where as compare to ICICI Bank 34 million which is in percentage is 24.54%,

Table 4 Shows Performance Analysis of No of E- Banking SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

YEAR	SBI BANK	% Change	ICICI BANK	% Change
2017	30	8.74	20	14.49
2018	38	11.07	25	18.05
2019	64	18.65	28	20.21
2020	90	26.23	31.45	22.70
2021	121	35.27	34	24.54
Total	343		138.5	

Table 4.1 Test of Hypothesis Testing:

H0: There is no significant difference in the Performance of E-Banking of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

Type of Account	Name of the Test	Degree of Freedom	Level of Significance	Value Calculated	Critical Value	Decision
Internet Banking	t-test	n1+n2-2	5%	4.2	2.69	Rejected.

Through T- Test, it is examined that there is no significant difference in the Net Banking users of SBI and ICICI Bank. It can be discernible from the table the calculated value of t test is greater than the critical value. Hence the hypotheses are rejected. It does mean that there is a significant difference of the Net Banking of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank.

Table 5 Shows Performance Analysis of No of E- Banking (Transactions) SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

YEAR	SBI BANK	% Change	ICICI BANK	% Change
2017	90	10.03	45	3.06
2018	130	14.49	115	7.83
2019	177	19.73	248	16.89
2020	220	24.52	380	25.88
2021	280	31.21	680	46.32
Total	897		1468	

From the Table 5.0. Performance Analysis of No of Internet Banking Users of SBI and ICICI Bank, In 2017 SBI Bank Internet Banking 90 million users in 2017 in 10.03% where as in ICICI Bank 45 million which is in percent is 3.06 which is lesser than SBI Bank internet Users. In the 2018 SBI Net Banking Users are 130 million which in 14.49% where as the ICICI Bank has 115 million in 7.83%.In 2019the SBI Bank has recorded 177 in which

19.73% of where as ICICI Bank has 248 which is more than of SBI Bank and 16.89% where recorded. In the year 2020 the SBI Bank has 220 which in 24.52% where as ICICI Bank has recorded 380 which is 25.88% which is more than SBI Bank. In the year 2021 SBI Bank stands at 280 where in 31.21% compare to ICICI Bank has increased around 680 which in 46.32% increase in the net banking compare to SBI Bank.

Table 5.1 Test of Hypothesis testing:
H0: There is no significant difference in the Performance of E- Banking Transaction

Type of Account	Name of the Test	Degree of Freedom	Level of Significance	Value Calculated	Critical Value	Decision
Internet Banking	t-test	n1+n2-2	5%	35.84	2.69	Rejected

➤ Analysis of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

Through T- Test, it is examined that there is no significant difference in the Net Banking Performance of SBI and ICICI Bank. It can be discernible from the table the calculated value of t test is greater than the critical value. Hence the hypotheses are rejected. It does mean that there is a significant difference of the Net Banking of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank.

From the 4.1(6) showing the performance Analysis of No of Mobile Banking User of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank. In the year 2017 SBI Bank mobile Banking is 37 Million users, which in 7.02%,where are as 28 million which is in 7.71%.which is less than of SBI Bank. In the year 2018, the SBI Bank has recorded 62 million users in 11.76% where as 25 million users which in percentage 6.88 % .In the Year 2019 the SBI Bank has 95 million users which in percentage stands at 18.2%, where as Compare to ICICI Bank 32 million which in 8.81% which is less than SBI Bank .In the year 2020 SBI Mobile banking recorded increase 135 millions users whereas as compare to ICICI Bank is 128 million users which in 35.26%. In the year 2021 SBI has recorded 198 Users which is 37.57 % of the users where as compare to ICICI Bank has 150 million users and in 41.32% of the which is less than that of the SBI Bank.

Table 6 Shows Performance Analysis of No of Mobile Banking User of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

YEAR	SBI BANK	% Change	ICICI BANK	% Change
2017	37	7.02	28	7.71
2018	62	11.76	25	6.88
2019	95	18.02	32	8.81
2020	135	25.61	128	35.26
2021	198	37.57	150	41.32
Total	527		363	

Table :6.1 Test of Hypothesis testing:

H0: There is no significant difference in the Performance of Mobile Banking Transaction Analysis of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

Type of Account	Name of the Test	Degree of Freedom	Level of Significance	Value Calculated	Critical Value	Decision
Mobile Banking	t-test	n1+n2-2	5%	42.95	2.69	Rejected

Through T- Test, it is examined that there is no significant difference in the Mobile Banking Performance of SBI and ICICI Bank. It can be discernible from the table the calculated value of t test is greater than the critical value. Hence the hypotheses are rejected. It does mean that there is a significant difference of the Mobile Banking of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

From the table 7.0 the total no of Point of Sales Business of SBI and ICICI Bank states the in the year SBI Bank POS were 2% recorded where as ICICI Bank was 1.5% which less than the SBI Bank. In the year 2017 SBI Bank stands at 8% where as ICICI Bank was 1.7 % which is less than 0.3% less than the SBI Bank. In year 2019 SBI has increase its POS Growth around 13% where as ICICI Bank recorded at 2.3% growth which is less than the SBI Bank. In the year 2020 SBI Bank has recorded growth of POS business around 17% where ICICI Bank are at 4.5% growth, compare to SBI Bank is very less. In the year 2021 SBI Bank has increase its growth of POS around 23% where as compare to ICICI Bank it is recorded less than the previous year of 3.5% which less than the SBI Bank.

Table 7 Shows Performance Analysis of No of POS Growth SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

YEAR	SBI BANK	% Change	ICICI BANK	% Change
2017		2%		1.5%
2018		8%		1.7%
2019		13%		2.3%
2020		17%		4.5%
2021		23%		3.5%

Table :7.1 Test of Hypothesis testing:

H0: There is no significant difference in the Performance of POS Growth Analysis of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

Type of Account	Name of the Test	Degree of Freedom	Level of Significance	Value Calculated	Critical Value	Decision
POS Machines	t-test	n1+n2-2	5%	2.6 8	2.69	Accepted

Through T- Test, it is examined that there is no significant difference in the Performance of POS Machines SBI and ICICI Bank. It can be discernible from the table the calculated value of t test is lesser than the critical value. Hence the hypotheses are accepted. It does mean that there is a no significant difference of the POS Growth of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

Table 8 Shows Performance Analysis of No of ATM (no of Machines) SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

YEAR	SBI BANK	% Change	ICICI BANK	% Change
2017	27286	12.17	9006	15.79
2018	31752	14.15	10481	18.38
2019	51491	22.97	11315	19.84
2020	54560	24.34	12451	21.83
2021	59011	26.33	13766	24.14
Total	224100			

From the Table :8.0 Show the performance analysis of no of ATM Machines growth of SBI and the ICICI Bank.in the year 2017 SBI Bank Total no ATMs machines recorded was 27286 which in percentage of 12.17% where as ICICI recorded 9006 which in percentage is 15.79 % which is lesser than that of SBI Bank. In the year the Total no of ATMS Machines of SBI Bank is recorded 31752 which is 14.15% where as ICICI Bank is 10481 which is lesser than that of 18.38.In the year 2019, SBI Bank has recorded around 51491 which is around growth of 22.97 % where as ICICI Bank has total no of Machines is 11315, in 19.84% growth which is lesser than that of SBI Bank.. In the year 2020 SBI Bank has increased the total no Machines to 54560 which in 24.34% where as ICICI Bank is 12451 which is 21.83 % lesser than that of the SBI Banking the year 2021 the SBI Bank has increased total no of ATMS Machines to 59011 which is 26.33% of the growth of ATMS and compare to ICICI Bank the Total no of Machines has 13766 which is in 24.14% lesser than that of the SBI Bank .

Table 8.1 Test of Hypothesis testing:

H0: There is no significant difference in the Performance of AMT Machines Analysis of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

Type of Account	Name of the Test	Degree of Freedom	Level of Significance	Value Calculated	Critical Value	Decision
ATM	t-test	n1+n2-2	5%	99.903	2.69	rejected

Through T- Test, it is examined that there is no significant difference in the Performance of ATM Machines SBI and ICICI Bank. It can be discernible from the table the calculated value of t test is greater than the critical value. Hence the hypotheses are rejected. It does mean that there is a significant difference of the AMTS Performance of SBI Bank ATM and ICICI Bank ATMS.

Table 9 Shows Performance Analysis of No of Kiosks (Machines) SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

YEAR	SBI BANK	% Change	ICICI BANK	% Change
2017	1165	10.07	250	7.18
2018	2196	18.98	525	15.08
2019	2583	22.33	780	22.41
2020	2595	22.44	800	22.98
2021	3025	26.15	1125	32.32
Total	11564		3480	

From the Table 9.0 SBI Kiosks Machine performance analysis in the year 2017 no of Kiosks Machines were 1165 which in 10.07% where as compare to ICICI Bank were 250 were in 7.18%. In the year 2018 SBI kiosks machines were 2196 which in 18.98 % compare to ICICI Bank were 525 which in 15.08 which is less than SBI Bank. In year 201 SBI Bank Kiosks Machnes increase 2583 which comes in percentage of 22.33, Where as ICICI Bank Kiosks was increased to 780 which in percentage 22.41. In the year 2015 SBI Bank Through T- Test, it is examined that there is no significant difference in the Performance of ATM Machines SBI and ICICI Bank. It can be discernible from the table the calculated value of t test is greater than the critical value. Hence the hypotheses are rejected. It does mean that there is a significant difference of the AMTS Performance of SBI Bank ATM and ICICI Bank ATM, Kisoks Machines were increased to 2595 which in percentage of 22.44 where as ICICI Bank kiosks Machines were increased to 800 which in percentage of 22.98 where as in the Year 2021 the SBI Kisoks Machines were increase to 3025 which in percentage is 26.15 where as ICICI Bank increased to 1125 which in percentage is 32.32.

Table 9.1 : Test of Hypothesis testing:

H0: There is no significant difference in the Performance of Kiosks Machines Analysis of SBI Bank and ICICI Bank

Type of Account	Name of the Test	Degree of Freedom	Level of Significance	Value Calculated	Critical Value	Decision
Kiosks	t-test	n1+n2-2	5%	80.229	2.69	rejected

Through T- Test, it is examined that there is no significant difference in the Performance of ATM Machines SBI and ICICI Bank. It can be discernible from the table the calculated value of t test is greater than the critical value. Hence the hypotheses are rejected. It does mean that there is a significant difference of the AMTS Performance of SBI Bank ATM and ICICI Bank ATMS.

Summary of Hypothesis

S.No	Variable	Null hypothesis
1	Performance Analysis no of Debit Card Users of SBI & ICICI Bank	Accepted
2	Performance Analysis's of no of debit Card Transaction (Spending)SBI Bank and ICICI Bank	Accepted
3	Performance Analysis of no of Credit Card, Users of SBI and ICICI Bank	Rejected
4	Performance Analysis of No of Internet Banking Users of SBI and ICICI Bank	Rejected
5	Performance Analysis of No of Internet Banking Transactions of SBI and ICICI Bank	Rejected
6	Performance Analysis of Mobile Banking Users of SBI and ICICI Bank	Rejected
7	Performance Analysis of No of Point of Sales (POS) Growth of SBI and ICICI Bank	Accepted
8	Performance Analysis of No of ATMS Machines of SBI and ICICI Bank	Rejected
9	Performance Analysis of no of Kiosks Machines of SBI and ICICI Bank	Rejected

VII. FINDING, SUGGESTIONS & CONSLUIONS:

The study examines the performance strategies of select banks towards e- financial services. The study examined the SBI and ICICI Banks secondary data and applied the statistical method of t test. The following are the findings have been derived with the result of statistical analysis.

- The study observed that the no. of Users of SBI debit Card has increased 39.5% in the span of five years i.e., 2017 to 2021 but ICICI Bank witnessed 32.6% growth in the same period. Therefore, it has been found that the SBI performance is found to be superior in debit card users compared with the ICICI bank users.
- The study found that the Credit card users of SBI increased to 4.68 million in the year of 2017 as compared to 3.7 million users of ICICI bank. The study found that in the year 2017 the SBI users growth witnessed 41.01% growth as compared to 23.87% growth of ICICI bank.
- The study found that the mobile banking of SBI increased to 198 million in the year of 2017 as compared to 150 million users of ICICI bank. The study found that in the year 2017 the ICICI Mobile banking growth witnessed 41.32% growth as compared to 37.57% growth of SBI.

- The study observes that the Internet banking user base growth has been compared with the SBI and ICICI bank. The study result indicates that the ICICI bank is able to increase the user base constantly high and reached 1480 million as compared to SBI with the 897 million user base.
- The Point of Sale – POS growth comparison between the SBI and ICICI Bank states that the SBI able to dominates its counterpart ICICI (3748 million > 2293 million base). The 2017 year growth performance e of SBI is found to be 17%, whereas ICICI recorded with the 3.5% in the same year.
- The study examines the No. of ATMs provided by the SBI and ICICI banks. The study states that SBI started with the 27286 (12.17%) compared with ICICI bank 9006 (15.79%). In the year of 2017 it has been observed that in the year of 2017 the SBI has reached to 59011 and ICICI bank with the 13,766.

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